

PHONEME RECOGNITION USING AN AUDITORY MODEL AND A RECURRENT SELF-ORGANIZING NEURAL NETWORK

Timothy R. Anderson, Ph.D.

Armstrong Laboratory
Crew Systems Directorate
Bioacoustics and Biocommunications Branch
Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433-6573

ABSTRACT

Neural networks that employ unsupervised learning were used on the output of a neurophysiologically based model of the auditory periphery to perform phoneme recognition. Experiments which compared the performance of a recurrent self-organizing feature map to that of the standard Kohonen self-organizing feature map show that the recurrent version performs significantly better (t -test, $p < .05$) in terms of phoneme recognition accuracy (30% vs. 25%) under the conditions tested (high signal-to-noise and 5 sentences from each of 10 speakers). However, the two representations make different types of broad class errors. The recurrent neural network classifier has smaller codebook size and lower entropy than its non-recurrent counterpart.

1. INTRODUCTION

The results of an investigation which attempted to improve the performance characteristics of the self-organizing feature map are presented in this paper. This study attempted to incorporate an additional characteristic of biological neural networks (i.e. feedback) into the feature map and investigate its effect on performance. This work was motivated by the observed inadequacies of the self-organizing feature map and other artificial neural networks which do not incorporate this well known and presumably important characteristic of biological neural networks.

The reason to include feedback was to provide state information, or short term memory, of previous network activity. If the network activity is similar from cycle to cycle, this indicates that the input for these two cycles is similar. If the network activity is different from cycle to cycle this indicates that the input for these two cycles is different. The feedback of network activity thus provides a means of determining the transient behavior of the input representation.

Most neural networks get this type of information by explicitly including multiple time slices in the input. An example of this type of representation is the Time-Delay Neural Network [11]. Other neural networks use both past and future time slices to classify

the present time slice. A well known neural network application using this type of representation is NET-talk [10].

2. AUDITORY MODEL DESCRIPTION

Payton developed a model of peripheral auditory processing that incorporates processing steps describing the conversion from the acoustic pressure-wave signal at the eardrum to the time course activity in auditory neurons [9]. Three sections are included in this composite model: a middle ear section, a model of the basilar membrane, and a hair-cell section that includes the property of synaptic connections to auditory-nerve fibers. All modules are based on published algorithms and current experimental data, except that the basilar membrane is assumed linear.

The predicated displacements as a function of time for 20 locations along the basilar membrane are used as inputs to subsequent stages of the model. The hair cell/synapse section of Payton's composite model predicts the probability of firing for 20 auditory neurons based on the 20 sharpened responses from the basilar membrane section. These stages convert the rms envelope of a stimulus into action potential firing probability as a function of time through the stimulus.

3. SIGNAL REPRESENTATIONS OF SPEECH

Historically, the short-time spectrum has played a major role in speech analysis. Specifically, Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) analysis has led to the development of one of the most useful tools for speech analysis -- the Speech Spectrogram. Previous work by this author has compared the performance of the DFT and Payton's auditory model for phoneme recognition [1, 2]. For this work the 20 channel output of the hair cell/synapse section of Payton's model was averaged over a 16 millisecond window every 5 milliseconds. The average of each 20 component spectral frame was subtracted from each component. The resulting vector was normalized to unit length. This representation was called the normalized average-rate response.

4. DATABASE DESCRIPTION

The speech data used for this work comprise a subset of the TIMIT acoustic-phonetic database [6]. All work reported here used the phonetically compact sentences of the first 10 talkers, 3 female and 7 male. These talkers were from 4 different dialect regions.

The labels used by Carnegie Mellon University (CMU) during the development of the SPHINX speech recognition system were slightly modified from those used to label the TIMIT database [8]. This CMU convention was also adopted for the present research in order to provide a better means of comparing results with other established systems. Thus, there are effectively 39 phones that are in separate categories.

5. SELF-ORGANIZING FEATURE MAPS

The neural network selected for this investigation was the self-organizing feature map [5]. This neural network was selected because of its ability to learn a topological mapping of an input data space into a pattern space which defines discrimination or decision surfaces. This process has been used by Kohonen in a system for phonetic recognition of Finnish and Japanese [4].

The operation of this network resembles the classical vector quantization method called k-means clustering. Self-organizing feature maps are more general because topologically close nodes are sensitive to inputs that are physically similar. Output nodes will thus be ordered in a natural manner.

Kohonen's algorithm adjusts weights from common input nodes to output nodes arranged in a two dimensional grid. Each input node is connected to every output node. Continuous-valued input vectors are presented sequentially in time to the network without specifying the desired output. After enough input vectors have been presented, each node's weights will specify a cluster center. These cluster centers approximate the probability density function of the input vectors.

6. RECURRENT SELF-ORGANIZING FEATURE MAPS

The recurrent feature map is based on a structure that implements the Kohonen self-organizing feature map as a three layer network (See Figure 1.1). The first layer is the input layer, it distributes the elements of the input to all nodes in the second layer (i.e. the first layer is fully connected to the second layer). The second layer calculates the similarity matching values or distortion measure for each node. In this case, as in Kohonen's implementation, a dot product is used as the similarity measure. The second layer connects to the third layer in a one-to-one manner (i.e. each node in the second layer is connected to only one node in the third layer). The third

layer implements a form of competition and selects the one node that has the largest activation. The recurrent feature map adds a fourth layer to this structure that is also connected in a one-to-one manner to the second layer. This recurrent layer then feeds back its similarity values to the second layer for the next network cycle (See Figure 1.2). The feedback from layer four to layer two is fully connected. Other connection patterns have also been investigated but results will not be presented here. With this connection pattern the number of weights that need to be trained in the network totals 70,656 compared to 5120 for the Kohonen self-organizing feature map. With this many weights the network requires significantly longer training times.

7. PERFORMANCE MEASURES

Several measures of performance were used to quantify and compare each classification scheme. The most common measures of speech recognition performance are the percent correct, percent insertions, percent deletions, and percent substitutions.

Other measures used to quantify the performance of the codebooks generated as well as the preprocessing schemes are the average cluster distortion and codebook entropy. The average cluster distortion is defined as the mean square error between a cluster mean, \bar{m}_i and its constituents,

$$D = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{x \in c_i} | \bar{x} - \bar{m}_i |^2}{N}$$

where c_i is the i^{th} cluster and N is the number of clusters.

The codebook entropy is computed as

$$E = -\sum_{i=1}^N p_i \log_2(p_i),$$

where p_i is the relative frequency with which code-word i was used in encoding the training set and N is the number of codewords or clusters.

Zue and colleagues [12] have shown how phonotactic constraints can provide significant benefit to the speech recognition process. In light of these results, measures of recognition performance at the broad class level were also made. Six broad class categories were used in this work: vowels, stops, nasals, liquids and glides, fricatives, and silence.

8. CLASSIFICATION COMPARISON

This experiment compared the performance of the Kohonen self-organizing feature map with a recurrent self-organizing feature map. The normalized average-rate response vectors for each phone

were presented to both classification schemes.

The calibration process used in this work is similar to that used by Kohonen. The process consists of the following steps. Once the self-organizing feature map is trained, learning is turned off and all of the training data is presented to the feature map. The node that responds to each training token is associated with that token. The token label that has the largest number of responses for each node is assigned as the label for that node. During testing, the token label of the responding node is used as the classification of the input vector.

Both classification schemes were tested using the leaving-one-out method on a per speaker basis. This method provides an upper bound on the error of the classifier and provides for better utilization of a limited sample size [3, p. 150]. The cost of using this method is that now multiple classifiers must be trained. In this work the data base contains ten speakers, therefore ten classifiers were trained and tested and the average error rates were calculated. This provides an upper bound on the error rate if this system was used for speaker-independent phoneme recognition.

Most speech recognition systems using vector quantization employ a codebook size of 256. To provide a means for comparison of results this number was used in the experiments presented here.

9. RESULTS

The results of this experiment show that the recurrent self-organizing feature map performs significantly better (t-test, $p < .05$) than the Kohonen self-organizing feature map in terms of recognition accuracy. Table 1.1 presents the summary recognition results of this experiment. The results for accuracy, deletions, and substitutions are significantly different for the two methods. The Kohonen self-organizing feature map had significantly higher entropy and significantly larger codebooks.

Table 1.2 presents the broad class recognition results of this experiment. The results show that although the Kohonen self-organizing feature map has better performance on fricatives (41.29% vs. 35.14%), nasals (11.87% vs. 7.76%) and stops (17.17% vs. 10.97%) while the recurrent self-organizing feature map has better performance on silence (86.02% vs. 74.09%), the results are not significantly different.

10. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper examined different self-organizing neural networks to perform speaker-independent phoneme classification. The study examined the performance of two classifiers, self-organizing feature map and recurrent self-organizing feature map in performing phoneme classification. This was accomplished by training self-organizing feature maps and

recurrent self-organizing feature maps with data from all phonemes, using the mean-rate response as the basis for the signal representation. The results of this study indicate that it is possible to assign an acoustic segment to one of 39 phoneme categories with approximately 30% recognition accuracy using the recurrent self-organizing feature map. The resulting context-independent phoneme recognition performance was comparable to that of the SPHINX System [7] with the same number of speakers in the training set and no smoothing of parameters.

Although the results show that the modification to the feature map structure results in no significant difference in broad class performance, examination of individual speaker results show substantially better performance on certain broad classes with one classification method than than other. This suggests a structure for a phoneme based speaker-independent continuous speech recognition system. One possibility is the use of multiple codebooks generated with different mechanisms (i.e. recurrent and Kohonen feature maps) as well as different input representations (i.e. DFT and auditory model) all operating in parallel. The outputs of the feature maps could be combined through the use of another, possibly supervised, neural network or Hidden Markov Model to produce the final classification. One type of multiple codebook representation is currently used in the SPHINX system [8] with great success. Three codebooks are used in that system. One codebook each for LPC cepstra and differenced LPC cepstra and the third combines power and differenced power. The output of these codebooks are integrated through the use of a Hidden Markov Model. The use of multiple codebooks with different structures, trained with different representations, and different learning algorithms is an area for future research.

References

1. T. R. Anderson, "Speaker-Independent Phoneme Recognition Using an Auditory Model and a Neural Network: A comparison with traditional techniques," *Proc. Int. Conf. on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, pp. 149-152, May 1991.
2. T. R. Anderson, "Speech processing using an auditory model and neural networks: A preprocessing comparison," *J. Acoust. Soc. Amer.*, vol. 90, No. 4, Pt. 2, 1991.
3. K. Fukunaga, *Introduction to Statistical Pattern Recognition*, Academic Press, New York, 1972.
4. T. Kohonen, "The Neural Phonetic Typewriter," *IEEE Computer Magazine*, vol. 21, pp. 11-22, 1988.
5. T. Kohonen, *Self-Organization and Associative Memory*, Third Edition, Springer-Verlag, Berlin,

- 1989.
6. L. Lamel, R. Kassel, and S. Seneff, "Speech Database Development: Design and analysis of the acoustic-phonetic corpus," *Proc. DARPA Speech Recognition Workshop*, pp. 100-109, 1986.
 7. K. F. Lee and H. W. Hon, "Speaker-independent phone recognition using hidden markov models," *IEEE Trans. ASSP*, vol. 37, pp. 1641-1648, November 1989.
 8. K. F. Lee, *Automatic Speech Recognition: The development of the SPHINX system*, Kluwer Academic, Boston, 1989.
 9. K. L. Payton, "Vowel Processing by a Model of the Auditory Periphery: A Comparison to Eighth-Nerve Responses," *J. Acoust. Soc. Amer.*, vol. 83, pp. 145-162, 1988.
 10. T. J. Sejnowski and C. R. Rosenberg, "NETalk: A parallel network that learns to read aloud," Department of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science Technical Report 86/01, Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, Maryland, 1986.
 11. A. Waibel, T. Hanazawa, G. Hinton, K. Shikano, and K. J. Lang, "Phoneme Recognition Using Time-Delay Neural Networks," *IEEE Acoust., Speech, and Signal Processing*, vol. 37, pp. 328-339, March 1989.
 12. V. W. Zue, "The Use of Speech Knowledge in Automatic Speech Recognition," *Proc. of the IEEE*, vol. 73, pp. 1602-1615, November 1985.

Table 1.1: Summary Results

	Kohonen	Recurrent
Correct	25.17	29.55
Deletions	12.74	23.27
Insertions	5.21	2.47
Substitutions	56.88	44.71
Distortion	0.99	0.99
Entropy	6.49	4.98
Size	188.00	149.00

Table 1.2: Broad Class Results

	Kohonen	Recurrent
Fricatives	41.29	35.14
Glides	34.27	35.85
Nasals	11.87	7.76
Silence	74.09	86.02
Stops	17.17	10.97
Vowels	61.31	61.25
Total	47.31	48.06

Figure 1.1: Kohonen Self-Organizing Feature Map as a Three-Layer Network

Figure 1.2: Recurrent Self-Organizing Feature Map